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D 5.7

Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (M18 UPDATE)

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#HYPOPPROJECT

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Deliverable abstract

D5.7 is the update of the Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of Work Package 5, updated after 18 months of project implementation. This deliverable sets out the actions planned to strengthen and improve the internal and external communication and dissemination processes of the HYPOP project. This report includes the final steps for scaling up DEC measures in light of the project ending in September 2025, to ensure maximum exposure to the relevant project target audience.

Keywords

Dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy, outreach, awareness raising, communication toolkit, target group, exploitable asset, result, impact

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Partners short names

ENVI	Environment Park Torino Spa
IMI	Institute For Methods Innovation
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
CNH2	Centro Nacional De Experimentacione Tecnologias De Hidrogeno Y Pilasde Combustible Consorcio
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
BH2C	Balkanski Vodородen Klaster

Abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement

Executive Summary

Communication and dissemination are paramount to the success and impact of project HYPOP – HYdrogen Public Opinion and acceptance, and as such this deliverable sets out concrete steps to obtain the foreseen results in these fields.

HYPOP has been making use of the EU H2020 and Horizon Europe projects' dissemination and communication best practices and following the 6W approach: What, Why, When, hoW, Where and to Whom to disseminate / to communicate.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an update to the reference documents D5.1 and D5.5 for strategically and effectively disseminating knowledge and information about the HYPOP project, as the activities come to the end of the funding period. The aim is to provide relevant information on the implementation of the Dissemination and Communication strategy, setting the next steps in terms of what should be done to ensure effective promotion and awareness raising about the project and its outcomes in the last 10 months of funded activities.

D5.7 wants to give the Consortium the right guidelines and tools on how to upscale its promotional activities and set out an effective process to follow for the promotion of the citizens and stakeholders workshops, activities that are crucial to reach HYPOP's goals and objectives.

1 Introduction

This document is an update of the First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan delivered at M3 (D5.1 as per GA), and its subsequent document, the Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation M12 update (D5.6 as per GA).

1.1. Context and background

Project HYPOP - HYdrogen Public Opinion and accePtance, Grant Agreement nr 101111933 is a project supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, and co-funded by the European Union.

Project HYPOP's Overall Objective is to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits, through:

- the preparation of guidelines and good practices that will help to define more effectively how citizens, consumers/end-users and stakeholders can be involved in the implementation of Hydrogen technologies
- the creation of a web platform, and social media, collecting communication material, mainly videos, on new hydrogen technologies, developed according to the early findings of the public engagement activities.

To reach the overall goals of the project, 2 different target groups will be targeted, engaged and involved directly in dedicated activities:

- the first target group brings together: citizens, consumers, end users and communication experts. The project will analyse the public understanding of citizens aged 15 and above in each of the Country or Region surveyed (Public Opinion Survey, commissioned by Hydrogen Europe in early 2022 and expected to be completed by spring 2023) with a deep focus on East EU areas (owing also to the involvement of local partners in Poland and Bulgaria).
- the second one includes the following stakeholders: First responders, permitting entities, certification bodies and decision makers.

Hydrogen is one of the key components of the energy decarbonization strategy of the Union. Its contribution is considered crucial within the main European Union Policies.

The development of Hydrogen technologies and their integration into the market energy can represent an important opportunity to face the challenge of climate neutrality and the energy crisis that Europe, its economy and its citizens are currently living through.

Public awareness activities are essential for increasing social acceptance and trust in hydrogen-based technologies throughout the European Union, particularly for addressing the potential lack of knowledge or mistrust of key stakeholders directly involved in the first phases of mass deployment in Europe.

1.2. Specific objectives, expected outcomes and impacts of project HYPOP

HYPOP strives to achieve the following specific objectives:

- Understanding public perceptions and reactions to hydrogen and fuel cell technologies
- Identification of the main individual-level determinants of public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technologies
- Enhancing involvement of citizens in the implementation of solutions contributing to the transition to hydrogen and fuel cells
- Understanding the pathways to influence public opinion by analysis of the current depiction of hydrogen technologies in broadcasts, newspapers, and social media, and from this developing a public information strategy
- Assessment of the specific role of the socio-economic and environmental impacts of hydrogen technologies
- Clear guidance on safety and certification and support to obtain permits and authorisations for installing hydrogen technologies
- Engagement on Hydrogen Technologies' implementation
- Identifying the safety approaches and the safety barriers in a range of different Countries, in order to create a map of the main requirements (certification) for installing hydrogen technologies and facilities
- Identifying the attitudes of the different countries towards social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) of the hydrogen technologies

Through its different operational activities, HYPOP aims to achieve the objectives mentioned above, whilst the transversal work of “impact maximisation”, which includes communication and dissemination, that is acting in its support: the aim being to **leverage results and bring them to an upper level, reaching the widest possible audience of relevant stakeholders and engaging them into the project activities (in line with the stakeholder engagement strategy of the project) and the exploitation of results.**

Below the main project outcomes and expected impacts:

- Outcomes:
 - Reach a deeper understanding of the public opinion on hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the social awareness, trust and reduction of the social distance to the hydrogen topic
 - Improvement of the understanding of the hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the scientific community and stakeholders' awareness of the public opinion on hydrogen topic, limits and possible drivers into the acceptance process
- Impacts: mainly socio-cultural (increase the knowledge and acceptance)

2 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of project results

Communication and Dissemination are essential to the success and impact of HYPOP objectives, its expected results and impacts.

Continuously sharing internal and external information is the transversal element that is being strategically and effectively carried out by partners for this first 18 months of activities, taking into consideration all communities relevant for and interested in the project.

The current document corrects and updates the progress achieved during the first year and a half of the HYPOP project, recording the challenges encountered, and planning the next steps to be taken in order to reach planned results for communication and dissemination objectives and to maximise project impacts.

This deliverable further elaborates on partners' roles and responsibilities when it comes to communication and dissemination activities, and the relevant processes and procedures to follow to ensure a smooth implementation and monitoring of such activities. The second part of the deliverable describes the continuation of the Exploitation Strategy, identifying the nature and value of key exploitable results (KERs) and a pathway for their continuous use.

The proposed dissemination and communications strategy has been following a 6W approach to ensure that every dissemination opportunity is adequately exploited during and by the project. The 6W strategy aims to clearly identify:

- **Why to communicate and disseminate:** For efficient communication and dissemination activities, the first point to be identified are the objectives of the communication and dissemination;
- **To Whom to communicate and disseminate:** Different communication and dissemination objectives will have to target different audiences; these different audiences have to be defined;
- **What to communicate and disseminate:** Different audiences have different interests and needs and will need to be addressed with different key messages defined according to the expected outcomes and impacts of the project;
- **hoW to communicate and disseminate:** Different audiences (Industries, Research Centers, Accademia, SME, Citizens, etc.) have to be reached and addressed through different channels. To be efficient, communication and dissemination activities must be well-coordinated and monitored;
- **Where to communicate and disseminate:** To fully reach its objectives, the project has to communicate and disseminate to all its target audiences and all over Europe; and
- **When to communicate and disseminate:** The project communication and dissemination both must run throughout the duration of the project, with long lasting and scheduled actions, and take advantage of opportunities that may arise during the project.

3 HYPOP Communication and Dissemination Strategy: Update

3.1 Project vision and objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy

HYPOP Communication activities have been dedicated to informing about the project's vision, objectives, strategic relevance, and key elements. Moreover, each month APRE is preparing an editorial plan highlighting HYPOP's activities in engaging with stakeholders and the general public. The editorial calendar includes the sharing of useful information about hydrogen opportunities and H2 projects currently running.

In terms of Dissemination measures, the Consortium has been active in participating in events and conferences to share the project's results among hydrogen key actors, promoting the outputs produced and the key takeaways from the project's activities.

HYPOP communication and dissemination strategy has successfully maximised visibility and achieved its objectives by actively engaging relevant stakeholders to support the uptake of its results. It has also effectively made the sectoral and technical aspects of hydrogen use accessible to a broad segment of civil society through the production of videos and infographics.

The present update of the Plan integrates the results of WP1 (T1.1 and T1.2) and the results of the public (WP3) and stakeholders (WP4) engagement workshops. The Strategy builds upon the results reached so far to implement the following changes and ensure a better reach of the target audience and KPIs:

- Continuing to share videos and infographics to raise awareness about HYPOP and topics related to hydrogen use and the application of its technologies;
- Continuing to address the most relevant doubts, concerns, and misconceptions about hydrogen as identified during the project's implementation;
- Share video interviews with key sectoral players to hear first-hand experience from the hydrogen sector;
- Share articles and interviews on local media to disseminate HYPOP's results and activities;
- Promote the "H2 Project Showcase" of the HYPOP's website, to create synergies with related projects, organizations, and institutions active in this sector.

3.2 Target Groups, Stakeholders, Audience, and Key Message

During the first months of the project, the partners have developed a map of Target Groups, which is composed of Citizens and Stakeholders who were to be involved in the project's engagement activities or could be interested in the project's results.

The key messages highlighted during the first months of the project have been developed through the implementation of different formats on social media. In particular, to answer the questions identified in D5.1, 6 original formats were developed and implemented throughout HYPOP's social media channels. The formats are: Glossary, Partner presentations, Hydrogen news, Hydrogen events, Hydrogen projects, and funding opportunities.

Do you know what hydrogen is, what its different categories are, and its applications?

If not, don't worry!

You can watch Prof. [Massimo Santarelli](#) and Prof. [Andrea Carpignano](#) from [Politecnico di Torino](#), [Ilaria Schiavi](#) and [Davide Damosso](#) from [Environment Park](#), dive into the world of hydrogen!

They will be your guides to understanding the benefits and challenges of using hydrogen as a renewable energy source and why hydrogen is an important piece in the path to decarbonization.

Watch the full video here: https://lnkd.in/eXp_9ExA

And check out our [YouTube channel](#) for the video subtitled in *Bulgarian, French, Italian, Polish, and Spanish!*

[Clean Hydrogen Partnership](#) [Hydrogen Europe](#) [#HYPOExplains](#) [#Decarbonization](#) [#RenewableEnergy](#) [#GreenHydrogen](#) [#HydrogenTechnologies](#) [#HydrogenUse](#)

Mostra traduzione

Example of content shared on social media

During these months of the HYPOP Project implementation, all Partners have contributed to the development of the dedicated Communication and Dissemination Plan and Strategy, in order to be in full compliance with the target results scheduled in the GA document.

HYPOP'S TARGET GROUPS

HYPOP's Communication and Dissemination strategy has identified the following target groups: citizens, consumers, end users, and communication experts (Group 1), and first responders, permitting entities, certification bodies, and decision makers (Group 2).

In the first year of implementation activities, HYPOP has mainly addressed the first Group through the use of social media. The reason is that the first Group is the ideal audience for the general knowledge formats that have been developed, while the second Group needs more sectoral and tailored communication materials, which will be based on the deliverables that have been developed during Year 1 of the project.

HYPOP social media channels and website have been used as primary tools to communicate about the important workshops foreseen for WP3 and WP4: the public engagement and stakeholders engagement workshops. These fundamental activities have been prominently featured in all HYPOP's communication channels, sharing with potential participants dates and details to participate in these events. Moreover, HYPOP's channels also featured the two international webinars, organized by project Partner IMI, promoting its dates and agenda. The recordings of the international webinars are now available on the project's YouTube channel and are also showcased on the project's website.

Check our workshops...

PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT WORKSHOPS

- 28th of NOVEMBER 2024 – IRELAND, Online
- 13th of JANUARY 2025 – POLAND, University of Gdnask, Gdansk 1-3pm
- 27th January BELGIUM, Hybrid event, English
- 17th of FEBRUARY 2025 – BULGARIA, Online
- 5th FEBRUARY 2025 – ITALY, Online, 3-5,30 pm
- 27th FEBRUARY 2025 – SPAIN, Online
- 20th of MARCH, 2025 – POLAND, In person @ Uniwersytet WSB Merito Gdynia

STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT WORKSHOPS

- 24th of JANUARY, 2025 – BELGIUM, Online, 9:30 – 12:30 (CET), English
- 27th of JANUARY – BULGARIA, Online
- 6th of FEBRUARY, 2025 – SPAIN, «Congresso National of Hydrogen» Huelva
- May 2025- POLAND, more info coming soon
- 21-23 MAY, 2025 – ITALY, «Hydrogen Expo», Piacenza

INTERNATIONAL EVENTS

- "Engaging Non- Technical Audiences: Best Practices for Energy Communication", Online, 20 March 2025, 1pm-2pm CET
- "Raising Awareness of Hydrogen: Best Practices from the HYPOP Project", Online 24 April 2025, 1pm-2pm CET

HYPOP WORKSHOP CALENDAR

Join us!
Contact: ilaria.schiavini@emvsnorak.com

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Clean Hydrogen Partnership Cofunded by the European Union

The General Engagement and Stakeholders Engagement Workshops on HYPOP's website.

The VIDEO/MEDIA section of HYPOP’s website, including the recordings of the international webinars, the videos and infographics produced so far.

CITIZEN AND STAKEHOLDERS

HYPOP’s Consortium has been basing its engagement strategy (for WP3 and WP4) on tailoring activities for specific Citizen and Stakeholder categories. Such activities and tools are explained in the table below.

The table has been consistent since the first version of the Deliverable (D5.1), since HYPOP is applying its Communication and Dissemination strategy reliably to ensure coherent and effective activities.

Citizen and Stakeholder categories	Key engagement	HYPOP Hub - Web Platform	Social Media	Expert Forum	Planned Events	Publication Repository	Workshops (co creation) Webinars	EU Technology pathway	Video/Infographics	Other Communication
Citizens with civil society organisations (CSOS)	Acceptance of citizens is needed for a technology uptake. CSOS will reinforce representativeness of their sectors/thematic focus for the benefit their members	X	X		X		X		X	
Experts from research/academia	HYPOP will increase the hydrogen technologies									

	visibility through promotion in experts' webinars, workshop, conference, podcasts, etc., and to increase knowledge-sharing with and between these stakeholders	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Businesses (industry, large companies, SMEs), clusters and business associations	These stakeholders will give first-end information on hydrogen technologies as they are early adopters/up-takers of new emerging technologies	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EU, national and regional policy bodies, governmental institutions, innovation agencies	Public authorities and specifically decision makers of hydrogen technologies will be continuously targeted to be informed and familiarized with the concepts of enabling technologies	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Other initiatives and projects	These stakeholders contribute to community building through cross-pollination and fertilization in order to increase synergies and networks	X	X			X			X	X

Table 1 - Citizen and Stakeholders involved

This table confirms that the Consortium has been effectively implementing the citizen and stakeholder involvement tools and activities outlined for reporting period M1–M12, in full accordance with the original plan."

3.3 Dissemination channels including Communication Tools

The HYPOP project has been maintaining an active and engaging online presence to continuously reaffirm its specific identity, connected to its objectives and aims. To communicate and disseminate relevant information and news about the project and linked topics, HYPOP has been successfully using the following channels, tools and activities:

- the HYPOP website (online from M4);
- HYPOP social media channels: LinkedIn, X (formerly known as Twitter), YouTube, Instagram;
- project news and communications published on the website and social media channels;
- project public presentation with a generic overview of HYPOP to be used in events;
- project flyer giving an overview of the project objectives, main activities and expected results;
- project roll-ups and banner;
- engagement with initiatives and networks in the field of hydrogen, both at the European and international levels;
- participation in major external events and conferences of interest (Sustainable Places, H2 Week, H2 Poland);
- information and knowledge exchange with and through other relevant initiatives for the exploitation of synergies;
- H2 Project Showcase featured in the HYPOP's website;
- HYPOP's videos on different topics related to hydrogen and its applications;
- HYPOP's infographics on hydrogen use and technologies;
- Awareness-raising campaigns;
- Publication of Press releases to highlight the project's milestones;
- Promotion of HYPOP's workshop (public engagement and stakeholders engagement) in the Consortium countries;
- Cooperation with the Clean Hydrogen Partnership.

The foreseen activities to be implemented throughout the end of the project are:

- More awareness-raising campaigns on hydrogen topics;
- Continue sharing of videos and infographics developed by HYPOP;
- Continue management of communication and dissemination channels (social media, website);
- Organize and share articles for local media to further disseminate project results and activities.
- Strengthened synergies with H2 projects, H2 Mission, and H2 Observatory with ad-hoc engagement activities.
- Continuous promotion of the H2 Project Showcase and connected collection of materials;
- Development of a "Useful Resources" section on HYPOP's website;
- Promotion of the project's Guidelines;
- Promotion of the project exploitation activities.

3.3.1 Project branding and toolkit

The complete visual identity, defined in the HYPOP toolkit, has been developed and provided by APRE to all Partners in the project Sharepoint. All the materials that compose the project's brand identity have been consistently used, both online and in print version, to ensure the implementation of a coherent and recognisable brand.

3.3.2 Acknowledgement of funding and disclaimer

As the beneficiary of support by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership, the HYPOP project has been constantly using the institution's logo, together with the EU emblem, in all its communications and dissemination materials, both internally and externally. Both logos, together with the identified disclaimer about funding, are also applied to every output of the project.

3.4 Planning of the communication and dissemination activities

To ensure the dissemination strategy remains current and effective, an internal process for planning, coordination, and monitoring has been established and is actively implemented. APRE, as the leader of WP5, is responsible for the development and execution of the Communication and Dissemination Plan across all tasks and subtasks, with the active collaboration of all project partners.

Each month, APRE develops an editorial plan for the following month, in which all relevant news, information, and events are collected to be shared on the project's social accounts and website. Partners are asked to contribute to the Plan by sharing all relevant news and activities they are carrying out, or sending information about events or conferences they are attending to promote their work in the HYPOP project.

Project partners are actively complying with the communication and dissemination strategy by regularly sharing news and updates, particularly with the citizen and stakeholder engagement workshops. These contributions play a key role in ensuring broad visibility of the project's activities and fostering inclusive participation, in line with the objectives in the Communication and Dissemination Plan.

Moreover, the Partners have been contributing to the H2 Project Showcase section of the website, sharing relevant projects to be added to the collection.

This process will be carried out until the end of the project's implementation period, allowing the sharing of relevant news in a timely manner.

3.5 Partners' role in communication and dissemination

APRE is the leading organization of Work Package 5, and has been overseeing all activities and tasks related to it, with the important cooperation and support of all Partners.

APRE develops original content and supports Partners in sharing their relevant news, events, and materials developed for the project.

The work task responsibilities are distributed as follows:

APRE – Work Package leader:

Leads the management and coordination of the work package, including:

- setting up of the communication and dissemination strategy;
- monitoring and coordinating the dissemination and communication activities throughout Europe;
- interacting with all partners for the dissemination and communication activities, and
- stimulating partners to provide dissemination input, such as news for publication on the project website, etc.
- drives the dissemination including communication activities;
- provide text of relevant news and publications related to general project activities;
- ensure quality control of the information provided;
- creation of a visual identity and provision of templates (Logo, Word and PowerPoint);
- production of promotional material based on the contributions from partners;
- set up and update of the project website;
- prepare and organize the distribution of the press releases (disseminated by all partners through their channels);
- ensure the quality of the dissemination towards experts, and manage the HYPOP expert talks webinars, dialogue and contact with “external partner” (ex. Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory).

All Project Partners:

All Partners (using the Editorial Plan developed by APRE):

- use the project’s visual identity for any dissemination on the project;
- provide contributions/material for public use on the project website and communication material upon request (e.g., use case descriptions, logos, etc.);
- provide news and/or communications on important activities and achievements related to HYPOP;
- inform APRE about possible participation in conferences, workshops, etc. related to HYPOP;
- provide short texts about participation in events for the news section of the project website (accompanied by related links and pictures whenever available);
- disseminate HYPOP information, materials and deliverables through their channels and networks, notably in the format of newsletters, press communications, social media posts, etc;

- regularly inform APRE about which communication channels and networks were used, and provide the required information for the reporting for the EC (see template in Excel sheet provided by a separate mail to the partners).

Roles have been carried out consistently throughout project implementation, with a good internal communication established among Partners.

3.6 Communication and Dissemination monitoring

Measurable targets and performance indicators have been set for the dissemination work. Besides the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) a monitoring is being provided with all the Consortium efforts for Communication and Dissemination activities in Deliverable 5.3.

Table 2 shows C&D project's KPI and their current status:

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
1	HYPOP's visual identity and related promotional	N. of brand identity kit released: 1 N. of social media banners: 2 N. of flyers: 2 N. of roll-ups: 2 N. of informative posters >2 N. of flyers distributed >2000	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large	All materials developed
2	Design infographics and develop informative videos	N. of informative videos to explain hydrogen and its application translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >3 N. of infographics to visualise project's outputs translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >5	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large	Ongoing, videos and infographics are currently being published on all channels
3	Website and social media accounts (LinkedIn, X, Instagram)	<u>Website:</u> N. of website online (M4): 1 N. of total visits: > 15.000 N. of countries reached >27 <u>Social media:</u> N. of accounts setup and active (M6): 4 N. of posts per year (total): >50 N. of social media campaigns: >5 N. of LinkedIn//X followers:	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large	Website online since M4, website visits around 5000, from 28+ countries. Social Media accounts set up (LinkedIn, X, Facebook, Instagram), 100+ posts shared on each social media account. 2 Social media campaign implemented.

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
		<p>Y1: n° 700</p> <p>Y2: n° 1000</p> <p><u>N. of Instagram followers:</u></p> <p>Y1: n° 1000</p> <p>Y2: n° 500</p> <p><u>YouTube viewers:</u></p> <p>Y1: n° 300</p> <p>Y2: n° 600</p> <p>N. of general local event per country participated by the local partner): >1</p> <p>N. of article/radio or tv interviews in national or regional media by local partners for each partner country: >1</p>		<p>LinkedIn followers: 600 followers</p> <p>Instagram followers: 154 followers</p> <p>YouTube followers: 9, 100+ views</p> <p>Events KPI achieved.</p> <p>Articles KPIs ongoing for Belgium, Poland, and Bulgaria. Achieved for Spain Ireland,, and Italy.</p>
4	Participation in external events and conferences and promotion through traditional media channels (*)	<p>N. of participation in events with dedicated booths: >3</p> <p>N. of speeches at events and conferences (live and online): >5</p> <p>N. of articles in newspapers, magazines or radio: >8</p> <p>N. of press releases (to 10.000 + contacts): >6</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large</p>	<p>Participation in events with booths: achieved.</p> <p>Speeches: achieved.</p> <p>Articles: ongoing.</p> <p>Press Releases: published 3 out of 6.</p>

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
				Remaining 3 are planned.
5	Joint activities with other initiatives and networks	N. of joint activities (expert meetings,): 1 N. of mutual learning workshop: >1 N. of online meetings with Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory: >3 N. of online meetings with EU Clean Hydrogen Mission: >3	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large	Meetings are ongoing. Meetings with Clean Hydrogen Partnerships: achieved.
6	Interconnection with hydrogen demo-project	N. of joint activities, demonstration event: 4	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large	Achieved.

Table 2 - Project's KPIs for Dissemination and Communication and related activities

An update on the dissemination activities has been made during the last General Assembly meeting (20-21 of May 2024) where the KPIs and their reach have been discussed by the Consortium.

The results of Y1 activities have generally been under the expected KPIs, and a corrective strategy has been developed and implemented by APRE and all Partners.

The main challenge identified—engaging followers on social media platforms—was addressed through the creation of project-specific content derived from the deliverables produced by the Partners, like the videos and infographics.

The project's communication channels were enhanced with visually engaging materials, such as videos and infographics, which proved more effective in capturing the attention of target groups that had previously been only marginally reached. Furthermore, tailored content was developed to engage specific audiences, with the support of sectoral experts capable of addressing their particular needs and interests. These corrective measures will be continued throughout the next phases of the project, including the implementation of targeted communication campaigns supported by videos,

infographics, and other engaging formats. In addition, project updates and materials will be actively shared during relevant meetings and events, further promoting stakeholder engagement and ensuring broader visibility of project outcomes.

A Dissemination Tracking File has also been set up by APRE to monitor the Partners' communication activities along the project.

4 HYPOP Exploitation Strategy

4.1 Introduction & Objectives

Clean hydrogen serves as a versatile and scalable energy vector, used both as a fuel and for energy storage, offering significant technical and environmental advantages. When produced via renewable energy sources—referred to as green hydrogen—it results in very low carbon emissions, contributing directly to climate neutrality objectives. Due to these attributes, hydrogen is considered a key enabler in the European Union's strategy for energy system decarbonisation.

Its strategic importance is recognised across multiple cornerstone EU policies, including the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package—particularly through the Renewable Energy Directives (RED II and RED III)—as well as the European Green Deal and the EU Hydrogen Strategy. These frameworks collectively position hydrogen as an essential component in achieving climate neutrality, energy security, and industrial competitiveness.

However, the transition towards a hydrogen-based economy is a complex and long-term process that requires coordinated involvement from a wide range of stakeholders: policymakers, regulatory authorities, technology developers, industrial adopters, end users, and—critically—citizens. Understanding public perception of hydrogen technologies, as well as identifying the needs, expectations, and barriers faced by technology providers and decision-makers, is fundamental. This knowledge forms the basis for effective policy-making, technological advancement, and increased societal acceptance, all of which are essential for the successful deployment of hydrogen solutions.

Within this context, the HYPOP project's Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation activities (Months 1–24), as outlined in Work Package 5 (WP5), play a pivotal role in supporting these goals.

As part of the preliminary exploitation plan, the Consortium—under Subtask 5.1.1: Target Groups Map—will focus on identifying and analysing the following key elements:

- WHAT the most relevant and exploitable project results are,
- WHO the key beneficiaries and target audiences for these results are,
- HOW these results will be made accessible and usable to stakeholders,
- WHY their dissemination and exploitation are vital for the broader uptake and impact of hydrogen technologies.

These activities are designed not only to ensure the visibility of project outcomes but also to facilitate their practical use, encouraging real-world adoption and reinforcing the HYPOP project's contribution to Europe's clean energy transition.

4.2 HYPOP key end-users

The identified HYPOP's key end users are grouped using the following categories.

4.2.1 Experts from research/academia

Specific Categories: Scientific Communities

Scientists and researchers, digital, industrial and social technologist, intellectuals and academic educators, and other profiles connected to the academical and scientific community, are interested in the results and impact of HYPOP Project. They have multiple interest on HYPOP topics (hydrogen for transportation, heating, energy). They can use them for networking purposes, inspiration, information, new research lines identification, new development possibilities, knowledge transfer, potential innovation projects as well as dissemination, reputation building, new areas specialisation, visibility and teaching materials.

4.2.2 Businesses (industry, large companies, SMEs), clusters and business associations

Specific Categories: Hydrogen Technology Manufacturers and Provider

Industry and large companies as well as SMEs and entrepreneurs are interested in new trends, new legislation, norms and recommendations. Looking for information to be more competitive, sustainable and integrated into society. Specifically, to be aware of the new legal requirements based on social and environmental impact conditions that are expected to be requested in next years (climate neutrality, clean energy production, green carbon free solution, etc.).

4.2.3 EU, national and regional policy bodies, governmental institutions, innovation agencies

Specific Categories: Decision maker, Public Authorities, EU and local projects, Experts on hydrogen technologies and communication

European Commission and other EU-level policy stakeholders have great interest to use Hydrogen assets to provide evidence and advise for new European Public Policies aimed to develop the competitiveness of Europe by integrating societal and environmental aspects (climate change, energy crisis, etc.) into technology development.

European strategies are followed by national, regional and local governments that, usually, try to be in line European Policies and strategies.

The target of the HYPOP project is to involve the following dedicated thematic networks:

- *National level: organization coordinating and representing hydrogen actors at the national level*

- *European level: European networks of actors involved in the development of hydrogen value chain*
- *International level: initiatives which link hydrogen networks and projects at the international level*

4.2.4 Other initiatives and projects based on thematic and methodological interest

Advisors, consultants and mentors as well as social and technological innovators are key-end-users.

They provide different types of services and vision related to the promotion, research, design, prototyping and validation, activation, dynamization and evaluation of technological pathways and future scenarios.

They allow the improvement and acceptance of the new energy strategy proposed to face and reach the challenges of climate neutrality and energy crisis in Europe, together with a change of citizens' perceptions for the proposed new energy solutions using Hydrogen Technologies.

Tailored exploitation activities will be included in a European-wide campaign aimed at raising awareness about hydrogen, promoting stakeholder engagement activities and enhancing the uptake of HYPOP's results.

In particular:

- engagement of the relevant Hydrogen Technologies Players and End Users
- define a project Brand identity that is consistent and easy to recognise, perceived positively by the different Target Groups
- provide dedicated materials (news, scientific papers, videos, etc.) useful to obtain the awareness about HYPOP's aims and objectives
- provide a better information about hydrogen and its applications, especially among young citizen, minority, etc.

4.2.5 Citizens with civil society organisations (CSOS)

Specific Categories: Citizens, Clusters, Territorial Associations, Networks, Hydrogen Communities

Professional associations, interest groups, the media, foundations, NGOs, cultural entities (with different age, gender and background), among others, may be interested in both the assets generated by the HYPOP project and the social, economic and environmental impacts that the introduction of hydrogen technologies entails.

These entities, in addition to exploring the potential social and green/ecological applications of hydrogen solutions, may also be interested in learning more about them to raise potential ethical and moral dilemmas such as transparency, open access to data, carbon free approach, new social inequalities, etc.

These debates have an impact on the media, on the Internet and on the cultural industries in general.

Important to include in the HYPO Project minorities, youth and elders with limited knowledge about hydrogen and related technological applications and solutions.

In particular is necessary to increase acceptance, knowledge and trust in hydrogen as clean energy source and valid technologies to use in different applications. It will be necessary to understand the effects of the climate change, energy crisis and the possible green solutions currently offered by the Hydrogen technologies available.

A significant opportunity for CSOS to have their voice heard will be the discussion on the indicators for the Social Life Cycle Assessment related to Hydrogen Technologies.

4.3 Planning of exploitation

The exploitation planning has been set up to ensure the following four objectives:

- support the project's engagement activities by reaching out target groups and promoting the initiatives
- ensure that project's outputs (such as guidelines, best practices and toolbox) are disseminated among the identified audience
- establish links and synergies with running projects and international initiatives in the field of FCH
- exploiting project's results beyond the end of the project, ensuring they are findable and accessible in the long term.

To optimize the HYPOP's results the best exploitation plan will be analysed, discussed and definite by the Project Team during the WP5 activities, and taking into account the interests and expectations of the stakeholders involved.

4.3.1 Steps for reach HYPOP's objectives

To reach the HYPOP's objectives, the following three steps has been individuated:

Step 1: Analysis

Step 2: Engagement/consultation of the Target Groups

Step 3: Results

Figure 1 - Steps necessary to reach the HYPOP's objectives

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has been providing an overview of the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan previously explained in D5.1. Moreover, this update aims to set corrections and adaptive measures to the aforementioned plan, with the goal of helping maximise the project impact and support the dissemination of project results.

The reaching of certain KPIs needs more finetuning, that has been foreseen for the second year of the project through the use of more visually engaging materials, that can help making the content more accessible and involving for different target groups.

Finally, the idea of tailoring the communication message to the engagement workshops support the HYPOP project objectives of raising hydrogen public awareness, creating a European community around the project and fostering the final HYPOP outcomes of guidelines development.

Results of the mentioned communication and dissemination actions will be reported in the D5.8 - Communication and Dissemination Activities Report and D5.9 - Networking with other projects and initiative Report to be delivered at the end of the project. The current Exploitation Strategy will be also implemented and finalised in the next deliverable D5.10 Strategic Exploitation Plan, expected at M28. It will give a comprehensive plan for the HYPOP's results exploitation and knowledge transfer creating effective impacts behind the project.

6 References

General Reference:

- GRANT AGREEMENT - Project: 101111933 – HYPOP – HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-2, 12/05/2023
- CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT - rev. 0, 13/03/2023
- D5.1 First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan – M3

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